

Recycling Surgical Masks and N95/FFP2 Respirators into Battery Separators

Aleena Nadeem, Seerat Hermain Zehra, Özge Kuldedeoğlu¹
Advisor: Assist. Prof. Dr. Çiğdem Toparlı

Department of Metallurgical and Materials Engineering, Middle East Technical University, Ankara, Turkey

Abstract

Pollution and hazardous waste disposal are one of the most crucial dilemmas that the world faces in the 21st century. Especially with the advent of COVID-19, there has been a tremendous increase in the usage and disposal of surgical masks. Thus, recycling surgical masks and N95/FFP2 respirators is critical to circumvent mask pollution. These experiments aim to recycle mask filters into battery separators by treatment with alcohols and strong acids at high concentrations to increase their hydrophilicity. Different procedures and treatments with varying chemicals and treatment conditions are employed for the polypropylene mask filters, and the results are bridged to the hydrophilicity observed. Produced separators are eco-friendly and cost-effective. They can be predicted to facilitate more accessible ion transport due to their highly porous nature and increased hydrophilicity. Hence, this approach can potentially be a leading step toward overcoming COVID-19-induced pollution.

Keywords: Battery Separator, Mask filter, Polypropylene, Hydrophilicity, Recycling, Pollution.

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1. Introduction

Even prior to the emergence of COVID-19, masks were still the cause of pollution due to being discarded in huge numbers from health institutions. However, with the increase in COVID-19 infections, a dramatic surge in their usage was observed. Therefore, the number of masks discarded monthly increased to around 129 billion [1]. If each mask is approximately 4 grams, then 516000 tons of the waste mask is generated monthly. As separating individual layers of these masks is a tedious process, these masks usually either end up in the ocean and landfills or are incinerated,

resulting in toxic secondary pollutants [2,3]. If in the ocean, microfibers will inevitably end up in humans, as a single mask can produce about 173,000 microfibers/day, which can be ingested by marine organisms [4]. As for landfills, these masks can interact with UV radiation to produce microplastics and aerosols that significantly impact the planet's climate, especially given the climate change issue [5]. Hence, it is of prime importance to overcome this significant issue.

As can be observed in Figure 1, on average, a surgical mask has three layers, amongst which the first and the third ones are made of Polypropylene (PP) non-woven,

¹aleena.nadeem@metu.edu.tr , seerat.zehra@metu.edu.tr, ozge.kuldedeoglu@metu.edu.tr

Figure 1. Layers of a surgical masks

whilst the middle layer is meltdown fiber. The middle layer, also known as the middle filter layer (MF), is the most crucial as it possesses 90% porosity, and its highly hydrophobic nature allows micro aerosol and dust to be filtered [6].

To achieve this hydrophilicity in polypropylene, different approaches, such as thin layer deposition, plasma treatment, graft polymerization, and physical modification, can be applied. However, one of the most feasible techniques that will be used in this experiment is acid treatment and dipping [13].

Traditional Lithium-ion batteries use glass fiber (GF) separators due to their high hydrophilicity [6]. However, they have some drawbacks as well. GF separator has irregular pore size distribution due to messy, winding fibers of various sizes and lengths, thus impeding ion transport. Additionally, to improve the overall efficiency of the battery, the thickness of the separator should be as low as possible to prevent the electrodes from touching each other and to increase the capacitance. The thickness of GF separators is about 0.3mm, whereas that of Mask Filter (MF) separators is 0.2mm, reducing the battery's efficiency [9-11]. Lastly, in the case of the MF separators, the raw material (masks) is already available, thus cutting down the cost of production compared to the GF separator.

Furthermore, MF separators have a moderate range for application and display high resistance to most conventional chemicals, along with better oxidation resistance properties when in contact with the positive electrode in a lithium-ion cell [11]. Thus, this shows the dominance of MF separators.

In the available literature, the recycling of surgical mask filters to produce battery separators was carried out via fuming sulfuric acid treatment. Testing this separator produced a smooth voltage profile with a low voltage hysteresis. This means that the Sulfonated Mask Filter (SMF) separator allowed homogeneous current distribution at the metal surface. Furthermore, the SMF separators showed more stable voltage profiles and better electro-chemical stability than the blank Polypropylene separator. These results can be attributed to the hydrophilicity and surface modification of the treated filters [6].

Our study aims to provide an alternative route for the fabrication of battery separators from mask filters. This was achieved by strategically replacing chemicals with more cost-effective and readily accessible ones. Various combinations of acids and alcohols were explored to obtain optimal outcomes. These alternatives introduced sulfur, nitrogen, and chlorine groups to the polypropylene filter, resulting in surface modification. Thus enhancing the functionality of the mask filters for applicability as battery separators.

2. Experimental Procedure /Methodology/ Design

This experiment uses different types of acids and alcohols to treat mask filters. The alcohols used are methanol, ethanol, and isopropyl alcohol (IPA), and the acids are 65% concentrated nitric acid (HNO_3), 95% concentrated sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4), 37% concentrated fuming hydrochloric acid (F-HCl) and distilled water.

Firstly, the mask filters with polypropylene structures are extracted from the masks and cut into 3x3 cm pieces. All three alcohols are mixed in a 1:1:1 ratio, and the mask filter pieces are put into the alcohol mixture for 10 minutes. Secondly, mask filter pieces are put into different acids at different intervals. 10 ml of each acid is used. Some of the filters were treated with acids without pre-treatment with alcohols.

All experiments done are shown in Table 1. The mask filter pieces are put into fuming HCl for varying time intervals (4, 6, 8, 10, 20, 30, and 40 minutes). Following this, they are quenched in concentrated H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 , separately and respectively. After these steps, the pieces are washed with ethanol and put into the furnace at 70 °C for 24 hours or longer until completely dry.

Table 1. Experiments

	Alcohol Mixture (methanol, ethanol, isopropyl alcohol)	Fuming HCl (37%)	Fuming HCl (60 °C) (37%)	HNO ₃ (65%)	H ₂ SO ₄ (95%)	HNO ₃ (65%) + H ₂ SO ₄ (95%)	Distilled Water (DW)/Ethanol Washing	Drying Temperature Time
1	10 mins	-	-	-	-	-	Ethanol	24 h at room T
2	10 mins	-	-	15 mins	-	-	Ethanol	24 h at room T
3	10 mins	-	-	-	15 mins	-	Ethanol	24 h at room T
4	10 mins	-	-	-	-	15 mins	Ethanol	24 h at 50 °C
5	-	2 mins	-	-	quench	-	DW	24 h at 80 °C
6	-	4 mins	-	-	quench	-	DW	24 h at 80 °C
7	-	6 mins	-	-	quench	-	DW	24 h at 80 °C
8	-	-	2 mins	-	quench	-	DW&Ethanol	24 h at 80 °C
9	-	-	4 mins	-	quench	-	DW&Ethanol	24 h at 80 °C
10	-	-	6 mins	-	quench	-	DW&Ethanol	24 h at room T
11	-	10 mins	-	-	quench	-	DW	24 h at 80 °C
12	10 mins	30 mins	-	-	-	-	-	24 h at room T
13	10 mins	30 mins	-	-	-	-	-	24 h at 70 °C
14	20 mins	30 mins	-	-	-	-	-	24 h at room T
15	20 mins	30 mins	-	-	-	-	-	24 h at 70 °C
16	-	30 mins	-	-	-	-	-	24 h at room T
17	-	30 mins	-	-	-	-	-	24 h at 70 °C
18	10 mins	10 mins	-	-	quench	-	-	24 h at 70 °C
19	10 mins	10 mins	-	-	quench	-	DW	24 h at 70 °C
20	10 mins	10 mins	-	-	quench	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C
21	10 mins	15 mins	-	1-5 mins	-	-	DW	24 h at 70 °C
22	10 mins	15 mins	-	15 mins	-	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C
23	10 mins	-	-	-	15 mins	-	DW	24 h at 70 °C
24	10 mins	-	-	-	15 mins	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C
25	10 mins	15 mins	-	15 mins	15 mins	-	DW	24 h at 70 °C
26	10 mins	15 mins	-	15 mins	15 mins	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C
27	10 mins	4 mins	-	quench	quench	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C
28	10 mins	6 mins	-	quench	quench	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C
29	10 mins	8 mins	-	quench	quench	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C
30	10 mins	10 mins	-	quench	quench	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C
31	10 mins	20 mins	-	quench	quench	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C
32	10 mins	30 mins	-	quench	quench	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C
33	10 mins	40 mins	-	quench	quench	-	Ethanol	24 h at 70 °C

To assess the water contact angle of the samples, a goniometer is used. The goniometer captures the photos of the drops and continuously evaluates the drop shape automatically. The liquid's surface tension and the difference in density between the liquid and the surrounding medium determine the droplet shape. The free surface energy of a solid determines the contact angle and drop form on that surface. Hence, with the water contact angles obtained, we determined the hydrophilicity of the treated filters.

A comprehensive video of the experimental procedures for a sample can be seen in the supplementary data. [S1]

Table 2. Water Contact Angles

Treatment Time (minutes)	Average Water Contact Angle (°)	Lowest Water Contact Angle
0 (Control)	110.144 ± 2.300	107.814
4	123.6742 ± 4.931	117.205
6	114.8188 ± 6.4227	106.919
8	129.709 ± 7.849	121.246
10	96.724 ± 5.421	90.262
20	123.9762 ± 6.5630	117.559
30	114.545 ± 4.257	109.448
40	109.9288 ± 7.4707	100.439

Figure 3: Scanning Electron Micrographs showing surface roughness for : (a) Control Sample (b) 4 mins treated filter (c) 6 mins treated filter (d) 8 mins treated filter (e) 10 mins treated filter (f) 20 mins treated filter (g) 30 mins treated filter and (h) 40 mins treated filter.

3. Results and Discussion

Since the hydrophilicity of our samples is fundamental to the functionality of mask filter-produced battery separators, water contact measurements were done on each sample. Water contact angle (WCA) measurement measures the angle at the interface between air, solid, and water. It signifies the wettability of a surface, in other words, its hydrophilicity. A low water contact angle shows the ability of water to adhere and spread to the surface of our material. On the contrary, a high water contact angle means water is unable to adhere to the surface and is repelled. In sessile-drop goniometry, the water contact angle is determined by the shape of a water droplet on top of the surface of the material being investigated. [9]

Different treatment combinations were implemented to determine which treatment gave our samples the best result. The lowest WCAs of each treatment time interval are tabulated in Table 2. The average water contact angle of the pure mask filter is 110.144° . It can be seen that the minimum average angle observed is at a 10-minute treatment process in Fuming HCl (96.6565°).

WCA against treatment time is plotted in Figure 2 for each sample.

WCA measurements of MF separators show scattered results for the first 10 minutes with a general trend of decreasing contact angle with increasing treatment time. A sharp decline is observed, resulting in the mi-

nimum angle to be observed at 10 minutes. Further increasing time caused the WCA to rise again, hinting at the filter's tendency to return to its hydrophobic behavior. This could be due to the change in surface properties and microstructure of the samples after treatment at different time intervals. However, the scattered behavior of the graph suggests a non-linear relationship between the treatment time and the separators' water contact angle (hydrophilicity). These anomalies could be due to the change in drying conditions for the 2, 4, and 6 minutes treatment time samples.

For the water contact angle measurements, it is essential that our samples are completely dry. All the filters were dried in an oven at 70°C for 24 hours after their respective treatments. However, if the samples were still wet, they were dried in the oven for another day. Due to time constraints, the 2, 4, and 6 minutes samples were redried using a magnetic stirrer for faster drying. This rapid heating might have caused surface damage to our samples. The trend in WCA due to surface modifications can be further understood from Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) micrographs of the samples.

As can be observed in Figure 3(a), the fibers of the control sample are completely smooth, with no trace of any bumps on them. At lower magnification in Figure 4(a), it can also be seen that the fibers are not entangled. From Figures 3(b) to 3(h), the surface roughness of the samples increased gradually as the treatment time increased from 4 to 40 minutes. The surface's

Figure 4: Scanning Electron Micrographs showing fibre entanglement for (a) Control Sample (b) 4 mins treated filter (c) 6 mins treated filter (d) 8 mins treated filter (e) 10 mins treated filter (f) 20 mins treated filter (g) 30 mins treated filter and (h) 40 mins

roughness can increase the treated filters' hydrophilic ability. This can be accredited to a larger surface area in rough surfaces due to small depressions throughout, thus increasing the wettability. Furthermore, it can be seen from Figures 4(b) to 4(h) that the fiber entanglement increases with increasing time. A reason for the increase in entanglement could be the increase in the molecular weight of the polymer [14]. The increased entanglement can lead to increased surface area and porosity, making the material more hydrophilic [15].

However, at higher times like 20, 30, and 40 minutes, there is a drastic increase in surface roughness of fibers, with even bumps appearing on the surface, as can be observed in Figures 3(f), 3(g), and 3(h). These bumps can be loose aggregates of carbon. This explains the increase in WCA since it becomes more difficult for the water to spread due to the hurdles present.

For elemental analyses of our samples, the Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) spectrum for the control sample, 4 minutes and 6 minutes samples is shown in Figure 5. The EDS Spectrum for 8 minutes and 10 minutes is shown in Figure 6, whereas for 20 minutes and 30 minutes, it is shown in Figure 7.

According to the EDS spectrum in Figures 5-6, an increase in the amount of sulfur and chlorine is observed due to the addition of sulfuric acid and fuming hydrochloric acid. From this, it can be interpreted that with an increase in sulfur and chlorine content in our filters by acids, there is an increase in hydrophilicity along

with surface roughness. This can be due to an increase in the material's porosity, pore diameter, and permeability, which causes liquid penetration to increase while the measured contact angle decreases [13].

Furthermore, as seen in the EDS spectrums of 20 and 30 minutes in Figure 7, the intensity of sulfur and chlorine have decreased dramatically. As seen in Figures 3(f) to 3(g), the size of the bumps increased from 20 to 30 minutes. One possible reason for this can be that with the increase in time, there is an oversaturation of carbon pores with sulfur, leading to the agglomerates becoming larger [7].

Due to the increase in sulfur content and hydrophilicity, our separators are comparable to sulfonated mask filters produced by treatment with fuming sulfuric acid.

It is essential to mention that despite quenching in nitric acid, N is absent in the EDS spectrums. Several reasons can be attributed to this. On some occasions, while conducting the experiment, some fumes were observed upon nitrogen quenching. Thus, it can be said that nitrogen formed volatile compounds by reacting with other elements or compounds and evaporated. It is also possible that nitrogen was present only in trace amounts well below the EDS method's detection limit.

4. Conclusion

Mask pollution is one of the significant global issues in current times. In this paper, experiments are conduc

Figure 5: EDS Spectrum of Control, 4 minutes, and 6 minutes

Figure 6: EDS Spectrum of 8 minutes and 10 minutes

Figure 7: EDS Spectrum of 20 minutes and 30 minutes

ted to overcome this pressing problem. The approach is recycling disposed surgical masks and N95/FFP2 respirators into battery separators. Per this purpose, the filters of different masks with a hydrophobic polypropylene structure are exposed to multiple processes to achieve a more hydrophilic nature and provide more accessible ion transport between the cathode and anode.

From different combinations of acids used, it was concluded that the treatment of filters with a mixture

of alcohols (IPA, methanol, and ethanol), followed by a reaction in fuming hydrochloric acid and finally quenching in concentrated sulfuric acid and nitric acid, respectively, produced the most efficient samples.

From the experiments performed accordingly at different treatment times, the 10 minutes treated sample in fuming hydrochloric acid was the one that showed the most hydrophilic nature. This is because the water contact angle was the lowest for the 10-minute treated sample. This can be due to the significant increase in the sulfur and chlorine content in this sample. However, no linear relationship between the water contact angle and the treatment time is observed. As the treatment time increased significantly from 10 to 20, 30, or 40 minutes, some bumps were observed over the fibers in our SEM images, which may show the deterioration in the filter's structure, preventing water from spreading at the surface. The mask filter-produced separators in this experiment are eco-friendly because they prevent toxic waste disposal through mask pollution. They are cost-effective since the main raw material cost only includes the collection of the said masks and not their production. The treatment procedure is also simple and applicable at small and large scales. Further research can be conducted to measure the voltage-conducting ability of the batteries with alcohol and acid-treated mask filter separators.

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6. References

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7. Appendices

Control (700x)

4 mins (50000x)

4 mins (130x)

6 mins (200x)

10 mins (300x)

10 mins (300x)

20 mins (10000x)

20 mins (5000x)

30 mins (20000x)

30 mins (1300x)

30 mins (1200x)

40 mins (70x)

8. Supplementary Material

[S1] A. Nadeem, “ADIMODTÜ project 22: Recycling surgical masks and N95/FFP2 respirators into battery separators,” 05-Jan-2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AONvM6x5nDM>. [Accessed: 05-Jan-2023].